

ARTS INTEGRATION IN DESIGNING LEARNING TASKS IN SCIENCE 9 FOR AN IMPROVED INNOVATIVE AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS

QUINN HANNAH DE GUZMAN

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The main thrust of this study is arts integration in designing learning tasks in Science 9 for an improved innovative and communication skills. Furthermore, it attempted to determine the difference between the pre-and-post performance of the students as to their innovative and communication skills. It also sought to find out the if there is a significant relationship between the performance of the students, their arts interests, and the perceived innovative and communication competence. Through a descriptive-developmental research design, the study determined the pre-and-post performance as to innovative skills and communication skills of the 42 grade 9 students at Bolbok Integrated High School, in the school year 2020-2021. Pre-and-post performance were employed to measure students' innovative skills as to arts conceptualization, process skills and design skills, and the communication skills as to grammar and composition, language use and interpretation and vocabulary. Also, the level of acceptability of the learning tasks with arts integration were assessed by ten subject experts from the same school. Results revealed that there is a significant difference between the pre-and-post performance of the students in both innovative skills and communication skills. This means that arts integration in learning tasks has improved the innovative skills and communication skills of the students. However, it was found that the arts interests and innovative and communication competency of the students has no significant correlation with their performance as to innovative and communication skills.

Keywords: arts integration, innovative skills, communication skills